

Leveraging multi-sensor remote sensing for monitoring moisture in tailings storage facilities

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Abstract: The EU-Horizon-funded project Multiscale Observation Services for Mining-related Deposits (MOSMIN) aims to develop comprehensive services for the geotechnical and environmental monitoring of mine waste to improve the safety, efficiency, and transparency of mining operations. Monitoring moisture in Tailings Storage Facilities (TSFs) is a critical factor for ensuring the geotechnical stability of these structures and enhancing operational efficiency through improved discharge planning, water reuse, and dust suppression. Due to the large spatial extent of TSFs, satellite-based approaches offer a cost-effective alternative to traditional in-situ sensors by providing comprehensive spatial and temporal coverage. In this study we focus on the use of satellite imagery (synthetic aperture radar (SAR) and optical sensors) for monitoring tailings moisture and water ponding in Tailings Storage Facilities (TSF). SAR is especially valuable due to its ability to penetrate cloud cover and its active sensing capability, allowing for data collection regardless of daylight or weather conditions. We test our methods on the Talabre TSF in Chile, one of MOSMIN's pilot sites.

Delimiting water bodies in TSF using SAR

Monitoring moisture in TSF using SAR

SAR is used extensively for determining the moisture content of natural soils as soil surfaces typically have constant roughness over time. This allows for the extraction of moisture estimates.

Tailings exhibit smooth surfaces when wet and are prone to rapid desiccation, creating rougher surfaces as they dry, leading to a relationship between SAR backscatter and moisture content. Salts forming on tailings are another complicating factor, acting as barriers to evaporation.

We introduce a novel product, termed *time since inundation*, which quantifies the duration between the current observation and the most recent instance of a significant drop in SAR backscatter. This approach leverages the principle that a sudden decrease in backscatter typically indicates surface wetting. Consequently, the time elapsed since this drop serves as a useful proxy for estimating relative moisture content.

Time since inundation (months) as of Jun. 24 2024

Website

Pilot Sites

Kevitsa (Finland) Boliden
Aitik & Laisvall (Sweden) Boliden
Roşia Poieni (Romania) CupruMin
Talabre & Ovejería (Chile) Codelco
Trident & Kansanshi (Zambia) FQM

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